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RUS VA O'ZBEK TILLARIDA TURIZMGA OID TERMINLARNING QIYOSIY TAHLILI

ANNOTATSIYA: Ushbu maqolada turizm sohasining ingliz va o'zbek terminologiyasi tizimining qisqacha qiyosiy tahlili ko'rib chiqiladi. Terminlar tuzilishiga ko'ra, ularning atamalar va terminologiya tizimlarini yaratish jarayonida ko'rsatkichlari tahlil qilinadi va ochib beriladi. Turizm terminologiyasini o'rganishning dastlabki bosqichida duch kelgan qiyinchiliklar turizm sohasida lug'atning etishmasligidan dalolat beradi.

KALIT SO'ZLAR: terminologiya, turizm, atama, tuzilma, komponent, model.

СРАВНИТЕЛЬНЫЙ АНАЛИЗ ТЕРМИНОЛОГИЧЕСКИХ СИСТЕМ ТУРИЗМА В РУССКОМ И УЗБЕКСКОМ ЯЗЫКАХ

АННОТАЦИЯ: В данной статье проводится краткий сравнительный анализ английской и узбекской терминологической системы сферы туризма. По структуре терминов анализируется и раскрывается их результативность в процессе формирования термино-терминологических систем. Трудности, возникшие на начальном этапе изучения туристской терминологии, указывают на недостаток глоссария в сфере туризма.

КЛЮЧЕВЫЕ СЛОВА: терминология, туризм, термин, структура, компонент, модель.

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF TERMINOLOGICAL SYSTEMS OF TOURISM IN RUSSIAN AND UZBEK LANGUAGES

ABSTRACT: The given article deals with a brief comparative analysis of the English and Uzbek terminology system of the tourism field. According to the structure of terms, their performance in the process of generating terms and terminology systems is analyzed and disclosed. The difficulties encountered at the initial stage of the study of tourism terminology indicate a lack of glossary in the field of tourism.

KEY WORDS: terminology, tourism, term, structure, component, model.

Introduction. Linguistic and cultural studies of terms open up opportunities for the study of many areas. Consideration of terms and their terminological systems in the aspect of linguoculturology allows you to look at them from several sides and attract more diverse information for research. "In world linguistics, a great place is given to the study of linguistic and non-linguistic factors necessary for the socio-cultural, economic and political ties of each nation with fraternal peoples, the solution of such priority issues as the formation of the terminological language of various industries and specialties." Among the wide thematic range of terms in Russian and Uzbek in the XXI century, the tourism sector is of interest to researchers. This is due to social, political and cultural changes in the world. The growth of globalization contributes to the increase of interethnic communication both in the Internet format and in real life. V.S. Senin writes about the important role of tourism in the modern world in the introduction to his dictionary: "In many countries, tourism plays a significant role in the formation of the gross domestic product, the creation of additional jobs and employment of the population, the activation of the foreign trade balance."

Analysis and results. Tourism has a huge impact on such key sectors of the economy as transport and communications, construction, agriculture, consumer goods production and others, that is, it acts as a kind of catalyst for socio-economic development. In turn, the development of tourism is influenced by various factors: demographic, natural-geographical, socio-economic, historical, religious and political-legal."

This topic has gained the greatest popularity and demand in the West, where the following definitions of the term "tourism" were given. Let's compare, Jafara Jafari: "Tourism is the study of a person who is outside the

territory of his permanent residence, an industry that meets his needs, and the impact that both a person and an industry have on the socio-cultural, economic and physical environment." Alistair Matheson and Jeffrey Wall believe that: "Tourism is the temporary movement of people to destinations outside of their usual places of work and residence. the activities they are engaged in during their stay at these destinations, and the infrastructure facilities created to meet their needs." "Since the second half of the XX century, world linguistics has been expanding the range of studies of terminology in various industries, considering linguistic and cultural problems of its borrowing from other languages."

Research in the field of tourist texts is divided into several areas: "Analysis of the theory of the issue allows us to identify three main areas of research in this area: terminological (study of the features of tourist terminology); lexicographic (reflection of tourist vocabulary in explanatory and bilingual dictionaries, compilation of special dictionaries of tourist terms); discursive (analysis of the features of tourist discourse on the example of tourist reference books, brochures, etc.)". Consequently, synonymy of terms is a phenomenon found in all languages of the world. Synonyms prevail in both languages. Synonym – the meaning partially coincides, but in terminology - synonyms that serve to express exactly the same concept. For example, in English, simultaneously with the term *adminstor* (administrator), he also expressed the term *receptionist*, used to denote. In Uzbek, this literally means "recipient" (in the Uzbek language, this is a variant of the term "administrator", actively used to refer to food).

The tourist terminosystem includes industry terms and terminoids, the addressee of which is recorded as a system. The term "researcher" refers to professional special lexical

units (professionalism), in professional colloquial speech (professional colloquialisms) and professionally refers to jargon (professionaljargon). At this stage, the term and professional vocabulary differ. Many researchers believe that these two layers of vocabulary coexist, and although they note that on an informational scale they are on the same territory, some (N.M. Shansky) assess professional vocabulary as a term, while others (T.R. Kiyak) consider synonymous terms.

Thus, the terminological system of the tourism industry has been increasingly in the spotlight in recent years due to the rapid development of this branch of human activity. The main areas of research in the field of industry terminology are:

- 1) lexicographic terminological activity;
- 2) unification of terms and term systems, implying ordering, standardization and harmonization of terms, editorial work on terms (terminological editing);
- 3) translation of terms in scientific, technical and other special texts;
- 4) creation of terminological data banks or terminological databases;
- 5) organizational and methodological activities of terminological institutes and centers at different levels - from industry to international".

The system of terms related to tourism has not been studied well enough. They can be proved by the following examples. There are many examples of tourist terminology in Russian, for example: surcharge for one stay – joy uchun qo'shimcha to'lov, visa application – viza olish uchun to'lov. They are part of the terminology and consist mainly of commonly used words and expressions. This suggests that this is terminology related to a common vocabulary. After all, tourist texts are intended not only for specialists in the field of tourism,

but also for ordinary consumers in the outflow zone.

Due to the fact that there are few real tourist terms in Uzbek tourist dictionaries, assimilation and adaptation of terms from other languages (mainly Russian) is noticeable. For example: travel agency – Sayohlik agentligi; reception desk – qabulxona; family hotel – oilaviy mehmonxona ; cooperation of guides – gid hamkorligi; transit (transportation of passengers from one country to another through an intermediate country)– yo'lovchilarni bir mamlakatdan ikkinchisiga oralik mamlakat orkali olib o'tish; passenger ticket – yalovchi taloni; direct flight – to'g'ridan to'g'ri uchish. In the course of scientific research, the predominance of multicomponent terms among tourist terms was revealed. The fact that it consists of complex phrases indicates its recent appearance relative to lexical units in the studied thematic group. Multicomponent terms have a complex semantic and structural formation consisting of various combinations of their components and consisting of a room with one, two, three and four bedrooms -bir ikki uch to'rt kishilik yotokli xona; luggage storage – yuklarni nazorat qilish xonasi; non-refundable ticket – puli kaytarilmaydigan chipta; luggage storage – yuksaklash xonasi; residence permit doimiy yashash uchun ruxsatnoma; customs formalities –bojxona rasmiyatchiligi; tourist bus turistik avtobus. Difficulties may arise when translating multicomponent terms due to semantic and syntactic inconsistencies in the structures of the Russian and Uzbek languages.

Considering that the tourism industry and its terminological system are under development, the corpus of words that make up the vocabulary used in this area is increasing. The enrichment of the dictionary of tourist terms is carried out in the following ways:

1) through work on mastering other languages. For example, borrowings from Russian to Uzbek;

2) the use of affixes and morphemes. This way of forming tourist terms is most often found in English. For example, the expression "ticket registration" can be translated into Uzbek by the term "ticket sale", consisting of one word.

3) combining the words into a hovercraft, the lessee is the lessee;

4) the fourth method is the most common, most tourist terms consist of phrases. Thus, in the terminological system of tourism, a larger layer is occupied not by one word, but by multicomponent terms:

In turn, international terms, which are very common in the field of international tourism, greatly facilitate the translation of multicomponent terms: FullHouse – the term means 100% occupancy of the hotel (all rooms are sold out) – barcha nomerlar band qilingani; Front desk - the hotel reception desk where guests are registered. In the field of tourism, there are more ambiguous terms, they are used less often than simple one-component terms. Terms with several lexemes denote the basic concepts of this area (sayohat journey, pilgrimage – ziyorat route – yo'nalishi; instructor – yo'l boshchi; dam olish maskani resort; transport – transpotirovka xizmati; flight – uchish. The analysis of tourist terms shows that in their structure and form, most terms in the Russian language have a substantive model. Among the analyzed Russian terms, two-component terms with a semantic model prevail: the mehmonxona tarmog'i hotel chain; (party ticket) group ticket – guruh chiptasi, (passenger service) passenger service yo'lovchilarga xizmat; the most common terms in the Uzbek language are expressions.

Among the polylexemic terms, the adjective-essential model prevails (tourism

industry, hotel complex, sightseeing tourism, off-season). The study showed that the most common complex terms are (suite, suite apartment, buffet car, hamroliqi guide, navigator) va (qiskartmalar yordamida tuzilgan atamalar (turoperator, ekoturizm, parvoz, sayoxlik agentligi, turagent).

Etymological research makes it possible to determine from which word certain terms originate, and to determine which model of word formation is used. Thus, the terminological system of the tourism industry has been increasingly in the spotlight in recent years due to the rapid development of this branch of human activity.

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As part of the study , the following were identified:

1. Tourist terms in Russian and Uzbek languages in this terminological system of tourist activity and concepts in the field of tourism correspond to the conceptual and terminological field, the micropole, and it is divided into thematic groups.

2. The formation of the tourist terminological system in the Russian and Uzbek languages of the past occurred in different ways. The terminology of tourism in

English is almost firmly established, in Russian and in the language itself - a developing system.

3. The big difference in the terminology of tourism in Russian and Uzbek languages, apparently, is the level of language proficiency. The term is mastered in Russian by 60.3%, in Uzbek - and in the native language by 6.3%. Therefore, borrowing the term "Russian" into the language is a productive method. The plural of Uzbek borrowings from bilingual term systems indicates a tendency towards mutual convergence. For comparative analysis of tourist terms in the Russian and Uzbek languages, scientific and theoretical ones were widely used in this research paper devoted to the study of formal structural and mathematical methods of statistics.

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